

Original Research

Determinants of Fraud Prevention in the Procurement of Goods and Services at Regional General Hospitals on the Island of Lombok

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Abstract

This study aims to empirically test and analyze the influence of Internal Control Systems, Leadership Styles, Anti-Fraud Awareness, and SiRUP Applications on the Prevention of Fraud in the Procurement of Goods and Services at Regional General Hospitals (RSUD) throughout Lombok Island. This study uses a quantitative approach with a survey method by distributing questionnaires to 72 respondents consisting of procurement officials, PPK, PPTK, and employees involved in the procurement process at Regional General Hospitals throughout Lombok Island. Data analysis was performed using descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression tests. The results showed that Internal Control Systems, Leadership Style, and Anti-Fraud Awareness had a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. This indicates that strengthening internal control mechanisms, implementing a firm and ethical leadership style, and increasing anti-fraud awareness among employees can reduce the potential for fraud in the procurement process. Meanwhile, the SiRUP application was found to have no significant effect on fraud prevention. This finding indicates that although SiRUP was designed to improve transparency and accountability in procurement planning, its implementation in public hospitals throughout Lombok Island has not been optimal or fully utilized in supporting fraud prevention efforts.

Keywords: Anti-Fraud Awareness, Fraud Prevention, Internal Control System, Leadership Style, Procurement of Goods and Services, SiRUP Application.

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Introduction

Fraud has become one of the most serious threats to the sustainability of organizations across various sectors. Beyond causing financial losses, fraudulent practices also damage organizational reputations and erode public trust in institutional systems. Fraud, particularly in the form of corruption, constitutes an illegal act carried out deliberately for personal gain. Unfortunately, such practices remain prevalent in Indonesia. If allowed to persist continuously, fraud poses a significant risk to economic stability and undermines national development. Its negative impacts extend across social, governmental, and state sectors, making fraud a major concern for the government, as it represents a key obstacle to improving public services and community welfare (Dewi, & Ariandi, 2017).

Data released by Transparency International through the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) indicate that Indonesia continues to face serious challenges in combating corruption. In 2023, Indonesia scored 34 out of 100, ranking 115th out of 180 countries surveyed. This score reflects a decline and stagnation compared to previous years. Globally, the average CPI score remains unchanged at 43, with more than two-thirds of surveyed countries scoring below 50. These findings highlight that corruption remains a critical issue, not only for Indonesia but also for many countries worldwide.

Many cases of corruption in the procurement of goods and services that come to light represent only a fraction of the fraud that actually occurs, as most uncovered cases result from reports made to law enforcement agencies. In reality, every organization—regardless of its form, operational scale, or activities—faces the risk of fraud. Practices such as embezzlement, misuse of authority, and corruption in procurement processes, ranging from simple to highly sophisticated schemes, continue to occur (Adenodi, & Eneh, 2025)

In the context of goods and services procurement, common forms of corruption include price mark-ups, bribery, embezzlement, fictitious procurement, kickbacks, extortion, abuse of authority, insider trading, nepotism, and document falsification. One of the most frequently identified modus operandi is price mark-up, where suppliers set inflated prices, even when the goods provided are not new (Ibrahim, 2023).

The high incidence of fraud, deception, and embezzlement within public institutions ranging from simple to highly complex schemes underscores the urgent need to build a strong commitment to the consistent implementation of good governance principles at all levels (Ibrahim, 2023). Fraud can be committed by anyone, affect anyone, and occur anywhere, including in local government hospitals.

In the Province of West Nusa Tenggara (NTB), particularly on the island of Lombok, several cases of fraud in the procurement of goods and services have occurred in regional public hospitals. One notable case involved corruption in the procurement of medical equipment at Soedjono Regional General Hospital (RSUD) in Selong, East Lombok Regency. This case resulted in five individuals being named as suspects in connection with the procurement of medical equipment budgeted at Rp 4.1 billion in 2008. The investigation involved the examination of 37 witnesses, as well as officials from the

Financial and Development Supervisory Agency (BPKP) and the Government Goods and Services Procurement Policy Agency (LKPP)

Another case occurred at Praya Regional General Hospital, involving corruption in the procurement of wet and dry food supplies. In this case, the Central Lombok District Attorney's Office named three suspects: the hospital director, the treasurer, and the commitment-making officer (PPK). The court sentenced them to eight years of imprisonment and imposed fines of Rp 300 million, along with subsidiary imprisonment of six months. Additionally, the former hospital director was ordered to pay compensation amounting to Rp 1.26 billion for state financial losses. A fourth suspect, acting as a supplier, was later named on June 3, 2024. This procurement project, conducted between 2017 and 2020, was found to have violated procurement regulations, resulting in state losses of approximately Rp 890 million based on calculations by the Central Lombok Inspectorate

A third case involved the North Lombok Regional General Hospital. This corruption case originated from findings by the Indonesian Audit Board (BPK) representative office in NTB, which identified deficiencies in project implementation resulting in losses of Rp 212 million. Subsequent investigations revealed estimated state losses of up to Rp 1.5 billion from a project valued at Rp 6.4 billion funded by the regional budget (APBD) in 2019. The former hospital director was sentenced to five years in prison in October 2022. However, the case was later terminated in March 2023 due to the absence of proven state losses, leading to the release of other suspects involved.

This study examines four main variables: Internal Control System (ICS), Leadership Style, Anti-Fraud Awareness, and the use of the General Procurement Plan Information System (SiRUP). The selection of these variables is grounded in two fundamental theories: the Fraud Triangle Theory proposed by (Cressey, 1973) and Agency Theory developed by (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

The Fraud Triangle Theory posits that fraud arises from the interaction of three elements: pressure, opportunity, and rationalization. Pressure refers to internal or external motivations that drive individuals to commit fraud, opportunity arises from weak control and monitoring systems, and rationalization involves justifying fraudulent behavior. Agency Theory explains conflicts of interest between principals (stakeholders) and agents (managers), often caused by information asymmetry, where agents possess more information than principals.

The SiRUP application, as a technological innovation in public procurement systems, is expected to enhance transparency and accountability, thereby reducing opportunities for fraud. SiRUP is considered a novelty variable in this study, as it plays a strategic role in preventing fraud by publicly disclosing the General Procurement Plan (RUP). Through this system, stakeholders can access detailed information regarding procurement packages and estimated costs, making the procurement process more transparent and easier to monitor.

Based on the above discussion, this study addresses a research gap by incorporating the SiRUP application as a key variable. Using a quantitative approach, this research

examines the influence of Internal Control Systems, Leadership Style, Anti-Fraud Awareness, and the implementation of SiRUP on fraud prevention in the procurement of goods and services at regional public hospitals across Lombok. The increasing number of fraud cases in hospital procurement has reinforced the importance and urgency of conducting this research.

Literature Review

Fraud Triangle Theory

Fraud Triangle Theory, proposed by (Cressey, 1973), posits that fraudulent behavior arises from the interaction of three key elements: pressure, opportunity, and rationalization. Pressure refers to financial or non-financial motivations that drive individuals to commit fraud, opportunity emerges when internal control mechanisms are weak or ineffective, and rationalization reflects the ethical justification used by individuals to legitimize fraudulent actions (Skousen & Wright, 2009). In the context of public procurement, these three elements provide a comprehensive framework for explaining how fraud can be prevented through structural, behavioral, and technological interventions.

Internal control systems are directly related to the opportunity dimension of the Fraud Triangle. Weak internal controls increase opportunities for fraudulent procurement practices by reducing supervision, accountability, and the likelihood of detection. Conversely, effective internal control systems limit opportunities by strengthening authorization procedures, segregation of duties, and monitoring mechanisms, thereby reducing the feasibility of fraudulent actions.

Leadership style, particularly ethical and transformational leadership, influences the rationalization component of the Fraud Triangle. Leaders who demonstrate integrity, fairness, and ethical role modeling shape organizational norms and ethical climates, making it more difficult for employees to justify fraudulent behavior. Through value-based leadership and moral guidance, ethical leaders weaken rationalization processes that often underlie procurement fraud.

Anti-fraud awareness is closely associated with both pressure and rationalization. Employees with high levels of anti-fraud awareness are more likely to recognize the legal, ethical, and organizational consequences of fraudulent behavior, which reduces their willingness to rationalize misconduct. In addition, awareness programs can alleviate perceived pressure by clarifying reporting mechanisms and reinforcing organizational support for ethical behavior.

The implementation of the SiRUP application plays a critical role in reducing the opportunity for fraud by enhancing transparency, traceability, and standardization in procurement processes. SiRUP facilitates open access to procurement information, minimizes discretionary decision-making, and strengthens accountability across procurement stages. By embedding transparency and compliance into the procurement system, SiRUP reduces information asymmetry and limits opportunities for collusion and manipulation. Consequently, the use of SiRUP contributes to rational, non-

discriminatory, effective, and efficient procurement practices, thereby supporting fraud prevention efforts.

Overall, Fraud Triangle Theory provides a robust analytical foundation for linking internal control systems, leadership style, anti-fraud awareness, and the use of SiRUP to fraud prevention. Each variable addresses one or more elements of the fraud triangle, collectively reducing the likelihood of fraudulent behavior in goods and services procurement.

Agency Theory

Agency Theory, as proposed by (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) explains organizational relationships as contracts between principals, who delegate authority, and agents, who are responsible for carrying out tasks in accordance with the principals' interests. In public sector organizations, particularly hospitals, procurement of goods and services represents an agency relationship in which the community and government act as principals, while hospital management and procurement officials act as agents. This relationship inherently creates the risk of agency problems due to information asymmetry and divergent interests, which may result in opportunistic behavior such as procurement fraud.

Internal control systems function as a key governance mechanism to mitigate agency problems by reducing information asymmetry and monitoring agent behavior. Effective internal controls enhance supervision, accountability, and compliance with procurement regulations, thereby limiting agents' opportunities to act in ways that conflict with the interests of the principals. Consequently, strong internal controls are expected to contribute significantly to fraud prevention in procurement activities.

Leadership style, particularly ethical and transformational leadership, also plays a critical role in addressing agency problems. Leaders who emphasize ethical conduct, transparency, and accountability align agents' behavior with organizational and public interests. Through ethical role modeling and value-based leadership, leaders reduce the likelihood that agents will prioritize personal gain over institutional objectives, thereby minimizing agency conflicts and the risk of fraudulent behavior.

Anti-fraud awareness among procurement personnel further strengthens agency alignment by increasing agents' understanding of their responsibilities, ethical obligations, and the consequences of fraudulent actions. High levels of anti-fraud awareness encourage agents to act in accordance with principals' expectations and reduce moral hazard, as employees become more conscious of monitoring mechanisms and ethical standards embedded in the organization.

The use of the SiRUP application enhances agency accountability by improving transparency and information disclosure in procurement processes. From an agency theory perspective, SiRUP serves as a monitoring and reporting tool that reduces information asymmetry between principals and agents. By providing standardized and publicly accessible procurement information, SiRUP constrains discretionary behavior and limits opportunities for manipulation and collusion, thereby supporting effective fraud prevention.

Overall, Agency Theory provides a strong theoretical basis for linking internal control systems, leadership style, anti-fraud awareness, and the use of SiRUP to fraud prevention in public sector procurement. These variables collectively function as governance mechanisms that align agent behavior with the interests of principals and reduce the likelihood of opportunistic and fraudulent actions.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), proposed by Ajzen & Fishbein, (1980), explains individual behavior as a function of behavioral intention, which is shaped by three key determinants: attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. TPB extends the Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980) by incorporating perceived behavioral control, allowing the theory to explain behaviors that are not entirely under volitional control. Within the context of public sector procurement, TPB provides a robust behavioral framework for understanding how individual intentions influence compliance with ethical standards and fraud prevention practices.

Anti-fraud awareness is closely related to attitude toward the behavior, as employees who understand the risks, consequences, and ethical implications of fraud are more likely to develop negative attitudes toward fraudulent behavior and positive attitudes toward ethical conduct. Higher levels of anti-fraud awareness therefore strengthen individuals' intentions to avoid fraud and comply with procurement regulations.

Leadership style, particularly ethical and transformational leadership, influences subjective norms by shaping employees' perceptions of acceptable behavior within the organization. Leaders who consistently demonstrate ethical behavior and emphasize integrity establish strong normative pressures that discourage fraud and encourage compliance. As a result, employees are more likely to align their intentions with organizational expectations regarding transparency and accountability in procurement processes.

Internal control systems and the use of the SiRUP application are associated with perceived behavioral control. Well-designed internal controls increase employees' perception that ethical behavior is both expected and enforceable, while also reducing the perceived ease of engaging in fraudulent activities. Similarly, SiRUP enhances perceived behavioral control by embedding procedural compliance, transparency, and traceability into procurement activities, thereby limiting discretionary actions and increasing the perceived difficulty of committing fraud.

By integrating these elements, TPB explains how internal control systems, leadership style, anti-fraud awareness, and the use of SiRUP jointly influence behavioral intentions and actual behavior related to fraud prevention. Thus, TPB provides a behavioral justification for the inclusion of these variables and clarifies the psychological mechanisms through which they contribute to fraud prevention in goods and services procurement.

Fraud Prevention

Fraud refers to intentional and unlawful acts committed to obtain improper benefits through deception or abuse of authority, causing harm to organizations and the public (ACFE, 2024). In public sector procurement, fraud commonly occurs in the form of corruption, embezzlement, collusion, and manipulation of procurement procedures, often involving individuals with access to strategic information and decision-making authority.

Fraud prevention is therefore understood as a proactive and systematic effort to reduce the conditions that enable fraudulent behavior. Effective fraud prevention requires addressing organizational weaknesses and individual motivations by limiting opportunities, discouraging rationalization, and strengthening ethical behavior. Internal control systems and digital procurement platforms such as SiRUP reduce opportunities through transparency, accountability, and standardized procedures. Leadership and anti-fraud awareness influence ethical norms and behavioral intentions, thereby discouraging the justification of fraudulent actions. Consequently, fraud prevention in procurement is a multidimensional construct that reflects the combined effectiveness of structural controls, behavioral influences, and technological support (Adenodi & Eneh, 2025).

Internal Control System (ICS)

An internal control system (ICS) refers to a structured process designed to manage and mitigate organizational risks in order to achieve operational effectiveness, reliable financial reporting, and compliance with applicable laws and regulations. ICS consists of five interrelated components: the control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring (Chen, & Zhou, 2020). In public sector organizations, internal control systems serve as formal governance mechanisms that guide employee behavior and regulate organizational processes.

From an analytical perspective, effective internal control systems directly reduce opportunities for fraud by strengthening supervision, enforcing segregation of duties, and enhancing accountability. In the procurement of goods and services, well-implemented internal controls limit discretionary authority and increase the likelihood of detection, thereby deterring fraudulent behavior. Consistent with agency theory, internal controls align agent actions with organizational objectives by reducing information asymmetry and opportunistic behavior. Consequently, the effective implementation of internal control systems plays a critical role in preventing procurement-related fraud (Abutabenjeh & Al-Omari, 2023)

Leadership Style

In this study, leadership style is specifically conceptualized as ethical and transformational leadership, rather than a generic leadership construct. Ethical leadership refers to leaders' demonstration of normatively appropriate conduct through integrity, fairness, transparency, and accountability, as well as their active promotion of ethical standards within the organization. Transformational leadership, on the other hand, emphasizes leaders' ability to inspire, motivate, and influence employees by articulating

a shared vision, fostering moral values, and encouraging commitment beyond personal interests (Gani & Fitriany, 2021).

From an analytical perspective, ethical and transformational leadership styles play a critical role in shaping organizational culture and employee behavior, particularly in the context of public sector procurement. Ethical leaders serve as role models who reinforce integrity and discourage tolerance toward misconduct, thereby reducing employees' tendency to rationalize fraudulent behavior. Transformational leaders influence employees' attitudes and values by strengthening moral commitment and organizational identification, which enhances compliance with rules and procedures.

Effective leadership also contributes to fraud prevention by strengthening subjective norms and ethical climate within the organization. Clear communication, consistent enforcement of rules, and supportive supervision increase employees' sense of responsibility and accountability in carrying out procurement activities. Therefore, leadership style in this study is not merely viewed as a managerial skill, but as a behavioral and normative control mechanism that plays a strategic role in preventing fraud in goods and services procurement.

Anti-fraud Awareness

Anti-fraud awareness refers to the collective understanding and sensitivity of organizational members regarding the risks, consequences, and prevention of fraudulent behavior. From an analytical perspective, anti-fraud awareness functions as a behavioral control mechanism that influences employees' attitudes and ethical judgments toward fraud. When supported by leadership commitment, anti-fraud awareness strengthens organizational norms that discourage dishonest behavior and promote compliance with rules and procedures (Limbong, et al. 2023)

Within the framework of fraud prevention, anti-fraud awareness reduces the likelihood of fraud by weakening rationalization and increasing employees' vigilance toward unethical practices. Management plays a critical role in establishing this awareness by setting ethical examples, reinforcing integrity, and creating a work environment that minimizes opportunities for dishonesty. At the employee level, heightened awareness enhances the ability to recognize, report, and resist fraudulent behavior, thereby supporting early detection and prevention mechanisms (Ibrahim, 2023). Consequently, anti-fraud awareness contributes to fraud prevention by aligning individual behavior with organizational objectives and ethical standards.

SiRUP Application

The Procurement Plan Information System (SiRUP) is a web-based electronic platform developed by the Indonesian Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency (LKPP) to enhance transparency and accountability in public procurement. SiRUP serves as an official medium for publishing the General Procurement Plan (RUP), enabling public access to detailed information on procurement activities, including budget allocations, work packages, implementation schedules, and responsible officials. As public hospitals operate under local government authority, the implementation of

SiRUP is mandatory in the procurement of hospital goods and services (Wardhani, et al. 2021).

From a theoretical perspective, the inclusion of SiRUP in this study is grounded in technology adoption theories, particularly the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). These theories posit that perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and facilitating conditions influence the adoption and effective utilization of information systems. In the procurement context, SiRUP is perceived as useful because it enhances transparency, standardization, and traceability of procurement processes, while its web-based design supports ease of access and system usability.

Analytically, the use of SiRUP contributes to fraud prevention by reducing information asymmetry and limiting discretionary decision-making in procurement activities. From an agency theory perspective, SiRUP functions as a monitoring and disclosure mechanism that aligns agent behavior with the interests of the principal. Simultaneously, within the Fraud Triangle framework, increased transparency through SiRUP reduces opportunities for fraud. Therefore, effective utilization of the SiRUP application represents a technological control mechanism that supports accountability and strengthens fraud prevention in public sector procurement.

Hypothesis

The Effect of Internal Control Systems (ICS) on Fraud Prevention

Define internal control as a set of policies and procedures designed to safeguard organizational assets, ensure the accuracy and reliability of accounting information, and guarantee compliance with applicable laws and regulations (Budiantoro, et al. 2022). An effective Internal Control System (ICS) minimizes the potential for fraud by limiting opportunities for misuse of authority, whereas weak internal controls may create conditions that facilitate fraudulent behavior, particularly white-collar crime.

This relationship can be explained through Fraud Triangle Theory, which identifies *opportunity* as a key factor enabling fraud. Opportunity arises when weaknesses exist in internal control mechanisms, allowing individuals to exploit gaps in supervision, authorization, or documentation. Strengthening internal controls reduces such opportunities, thereby decreasing the likelihood of fraud in procurement activities. (Reskia, 2022) emphasize that improved internal control implementation enhances the quality of financial reporting and plays a significant role in fraud prevention.

Furthermore, prior empirical studies support this theoretical argument. (Wardhani, & Martani, 2021) find that internal control systems have a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention, particularly in public sector organizations. These findings suggest that effective controls such as segregation of duties, authorization procedures, and continuous monitoring serve as critical deterrents against fraudulent actions.

From an Agency Theory perspective, internal control systems function as monitoring mechanisms to reduce agency problems between principals and agents. In public

hospitals, agents involved in procurement may possess discretionary power and access to information that principals cannot fully observe. A robust ICS reduces information asymmetry and moral hazard, ensuring that agents act in accordance with organizational objectives rather than personal interests.

Accordingly, an effective internal control system not only limits opportunities for fraud but also strengthens governance and accountability in procurement processes. Therefore, it is expected that the implementation of a strong internal control system will enhance fraud prevention in goods and services procurement at Regional General Hospitals across Lombok Island. Based on the above discussion, the hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H₁: Internal Control Systems Have a Positive Effect on the Prevention of Fraud in the Procurement of Goods and Services in Regional Public Hospitals on the Island of Lombok.

The Influence of Leadership Style on Fraud Prevention

Leadership style plays a critical role in shaping organizational behavior and ethical standards, particularly in environments where authority and discretion are inherent in decision-making processes. Power exercised through leadership can either facilitate or prevent fraud, depending on how leaders influence, motivate, and supervise their subordinates. Leadership style refers to a leader's behavioral pattern in directing and influencing group members to achieve organizational objectives (Adenodi & Eneh, 2025).

From the perspective of Fraud Triangle Theory, leadership style is closely related to the *opportunity* and *rationalization* components. Weak or permissive leadership may create opportunities for fraud by tolerating unethical behavior or failing to enforce rules consistently. Conversely, ethical and participative leadership styles reduce opportunities for fraud by strengthening supervision and promoting accountability. Additionally, leaders who demonstrate integrity and fairness limit subordinates' ability to rationalize fraudulent behavior.

In line with Agency Theory, leaders act as agents who possess authority and control over resources and processes, including procurement activities. Effective leadership reduces agency problems by aligning employees' behavior with organizational goals through clear direction, motivation, and monitoring. Leadership styles that emphasize transparency, delegation, and fair reward systems help mitigate moral hazard and discourage opportunistic behavior among subordinates.

Furthermore, based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), leadership style influences employees' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Leaders who motivate, recognize performance, and enforce ethical standards shape positive attitudes toward compliance and establish strong social norms against fraud. At the same time, consistent supervision enhances perceived behavioral control by signaling that fraudulent actions are likely to be detected and sanctioned, thereby reducing fraudulent intentions.

Empirical evidence supports this theoretical framework. Previous studies by Setiawan, et al. (2020), and Ramadani, et al. (2023) demonstrate that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. These findings indicate that appropriate leadership styles foster ethical behavior and reduce the likelihood of fraud in organizational settings.

Accordingly, effective leadership is essential in minimizing fraud in procurement processes at public hospitals. Leaders who motivate, provide clear guidance, and uphold ethical values contribute to a work environment that discourages fraudulent practices. Therefore, the second hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H₂: Leadership style has a positive effect on the prevention of fraud in the procurement of goods and services in regional public hospitals on the island of Lombok

The Effect of Anti-Fraud Awareness on Fraud Prevention

Anti-fraud awareness refers to organizational efforts aimed at fostering employees' understanding of the importance of fraud prevention and ethical behavior. (Ibrahim, 2023) emphasizes that, in addition to internal control systems, increasing awareness of fraud is a crucial preventive measure. Similarly, Bank Indonesia defines anti-fraud awareness as a collective effort to build consciousness among all organizational members regarding the necessity of fraud prevention. High levels of anti-fraud awareness encourage individuals to recognize the risks and consequences of fraudulent behavior, thereby discouraging involvement in such acts.

From the perspective of Agency Theory, fraud may arise due to conflicting interests and information asymmetry between principals and agents. In such conditions, agents may exploit their superior information for personal benefit. Anti-fraud awareness functions as a behavioral control mechanism that aligns agents' interests with organizational objectives by promoting ethical values and accountability. Increased awareness reduces opportunistic behavior and mitigates moral hazard, thereby lowering the risk of fraud.

Furthermore, anti-fraud awareness can be explained through the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB). Awareness programs influence individuals' attitudes toward fraud by reinforcing the negative consequences of unethical behavior. They also strengthen subjective norms by creating a shared organizational culture that condemns fraud, while enhancing perceived behavioral control by increasing employees' understanding of detection mechanisms and sanctions. As a result, employees' intentions to commit fraud are weakened.

Empirical studies support this theoretical argument. (Reskia, 2022) finds that anti-fraud awareness has a positive and significant effect on fraud prevention. These findings suggest that organizations that consistently promote anti-fraud values are better equipped to prevent fraudulent practices, including fraud in procurement activities.

Accordingly, strengthening anti-fraud awareness within public hospitals is essential for minimizing fraud in goods and services procurement. By fostering ethical awareness and collective responsibility, organizations can create an environment that actively

discourages fraudulent behavior. Therefore, the third hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H₃: Anti-fraud awareness has a positive effect on the prevention of fraud in the procurement of goods and services in regional public hospitals on the island of Lombok.

The Effect of SiRUP Application on Fraud Prevention

The General Procurement Plan Information System (Sistem Informasi Rencana Umum Pengadaan / SiRUP) is a web-based integrated electronic system developed by the National Public Procurement Agency (LKPP) as part of Indonesia's public procurement reform. SiRUP functions as a platform for announcing the General Procurement Plan (RUP), enabling all stakeholders, including the public, to access information on planned government procurement activities. Through this mechanism, SiRUP promotes transparency and public oversight in the procurement process.

From the perspective of Fraud Triangle Theory, fraud is likely to occur when *opportunity* exists due to weak controls or lack of transparency. The implementation of SiRUP reduces such opportunities by making procurement plans publicly accessible, thereby limiting discretionary power and information concealment by procurement officials. Increased transparency through SiRUP narrows the space for manipulation, collusion, and unauthorized procurement practices.

In line with Agency Theory, SiRUP serves as an information-sharing mechanism that reduces information asymmetry between principals (government and society) and agents (procurement officials). By publicly disclosing procurement plans, SiRUP strengthens accountability and constrains opportunistic behavior by agents, thereby mitigating moral hazard in procurement activities.

Furthermore, based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the use of SiRUP enhances perceived behavioral control by signaling that procurement activities are visible, traceable, and subject to public scrutiny. This condition discourages fraudulent intentions, as individuals perceive a higher likelihood of detection and sanctions. In addition, transparency norms established through SiRUP reinforce ethical behavior within procurement units. Overall, the SiRUP application is designed to prevent fraud and inefficiency in public procurement by improving transparency, accountability, and consistency between procurement planning and budget realization. This objective is aligned with the principles of public procurement outlined in Presidential Regulation No. 16 of 2018, which emphasize efficiency, effectiveness, transparency, openness, fair competition, and accountability. Therefore, the fourth hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H₄: The SiRUP application has a positive effect on the prevention of fraud in the procurement of goods and services at regional public hospitals throughout Lombok Island.

Research Model

Figure 1. Research Model

Based on Figure 1, this study's conceptual framework illustrates the relationships between Internal Control Systems (X1), Leadership Style (X2), Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3), and the use of the SiRUP application (X4) on Fraud Prevention (Y) in the procurement of goods and services at Regional Public Hospitals (RSUD). This framework is developed by integrating Fraud Triangle Theory, Agency Theory, and the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as the main theoretical foundations.

Internal control systems (X1) function as a structural mechanism that directly contributes to fraud prevention. According to Fraud Triangle Theory, weak internal controls increase opportunities for fraud, particularly in procurement activities that involve high authority and access to information. From the perspective of Agency Theory, internal controls help reduce information asymmetry and opportunistic behavior by agents, thereby aligning the interests of agents and principals. Therefore, effective internal control systems are expected to minimize opportunities for fraudulent practices in public procurement.

Leadership style (X2) plays an important role in shaping ethical behavior and organizational culture. Ethical and transformational leadership emphasizes integrity, role modeling, and moral values, which influence employees' attitudes and behaviors. Within the Fraud Triangle framework, effective leadership can reduce fraud rationalization, while in TPB, leadership affects subjective norms that shape individuals' intentions to behave ethically. Consequently, an appropriate leadership style is expected to strengthen fraud prevention efforts.

Anti-fraud awareness (X3) represents an individual behavioral factor that influences employees' attitudes and intentions toward ethical conduct. Based on TPB, higher anti-fraud awareness enhances negative attitudes toward fraudulent behavior and increases perceived consequences of fraud. This awareness weakens the rationalization element of the Fraud Triangle, thereby reducing the likelihood of fraud in procurement processes.

The SiRUP application (X4) is positioned as a technology-based control mechanism that promotes transparency and accountability in government procurement. Drawing on technology adoption theories such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and UTAUT, the effective use of information systems improves compliance when the system is perceived as useful and easy to use. From an Agency Theory perspective, SiRUP reduces information asymmetry through public disclosure of procurement plans. In addition, the transparency generated by SiRUP lowers opportunities for fraud, consistent with the Fraud Triangle Theory.

Overall, the conceptual framework emphasizes that fraud prevention in public procurement is influenced by a combination of organizational, behavioral, and technological factors. The integration of these theoretical perspectives provides a comprehensive explanation of how internal controls, leadership style, anti-fraud awareness, and information technology jointly contribute to effective fraud prevention.

Material and Methods

This study employs an associative research design with a quantitative approach to examine the effects of internal control systems, leadership styles, anti-fraud awareness, and the use of the SiRUP application on fraud prevention in goods and services procurement. The research was conducted in Regional General Hospitals (RSUD) across Lombok Island, Indonesia, covering five districts/cities. The study population comprises hospital employees; however, given that procurement activities are highly specialized and restricted to specific organizational roles, purposive sampling was applied to ensure the relevance and validity of the data. Respondents were selected based on their direct involvement and sufficient experience in procurement processes, including the Director, Deputy Director of Finance, Head of Goods and Services Procurement, Commitment-Making Officers (PPK), accounting and finance staff, and internal auditors. Random sampling was considered less appropriate, as it could include respondents with limited exposure to procurement-related activities, potentially reducing the accuracy of the findings.

A total of 72 respondents participated in the study. This sample size is considered adequate for analysis using Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), which is particularly suitable for predictive research, complex structural models, and relatively small sample sizes. Following the ten-times rule, the minimum required sample size is ten times the largest number of structural paths directed at a single latent construct; in this study, this requirement was satisfied. Although purposive sampling limits the generalizability of the findings beyond the study context, potential selection bias was mitigated by involving respondents from multiple hospitals and various hierarchical levels across all districts/cities on Lombok Island.

Primary data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed based on an extensive review of prior literature and empirical studies related to internal control systems, leadership styles, anti-fraud awareness, information system utilization, and fraud prevention. Measurement items were adapted from previously validated instruments and modified to suit the context of goods and services procurement in public hospitals. Responses were measured using a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Prior to full-scale data collection, the questionnaire underwent content validation through expert judgment involving academics and practitioners in public sector accounting and procurement. A pilot test was also conducted to ensure clarity, consistency, and comprehensibility of the measurement items. Construct validity and reliability were subsequently assessed during the measurement model evaluation using indicator loadings, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability, and average variance extracted (AVE).

Given that data were collected through a single self-administered questionnaire, the potential for common method bias was considered. To reduce this risk, procedural remedies were implemented, including assuring respondent anonymity, using neutral and clear item wording, and arranging questionnaire items to minimize response pattern bias. In addition, common method bias was statistically assessed using the full collinearity variance inflation factor (VIF) approach, where VIF values below the recommended threshold indicate that common method bias is unlikely to threaten the validity of the results.

Data analysis was performed using Partial Least Squares–Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with Smart PLS version 4 software. This analysis followed a two-stage approach, namely measurement model evaluation and structural model assessment. The measurement model was evaluated based on indicator reliability, internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. The structural model assessment included examining path coefficients, coefficients of determination (R^2), effect sizes (f^2), and predictive relevance (Q^2). Hypothesis testing was performed using the bootstrapping procedure to generate t-statistics, p-values, and confidence intervals for the estimated relationships. Although global model fit indices such as χ^2 , CFI, and RMSEA are often used in covariance-based SEM, PLS-SEM emphasizes predictive accuracy over overall model fit. Therefore, model fit in this study was evaluated using PLS-SEM-specific criteria.

Research Instruments

The instrument used in this study was a questionnaire containing several specific questions related to the variables under study. The instrument was compiled based on indicators contained in the research variables, which were described in the questionnaire items.

The Internal Control System variable (X1) is operationalized based on five main components that refer to the COSO framework, namely control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring. The control environment reflects the organization's commitment to ethical values and integrity. Risk assessment describes the organization's ability to identify and analyze risks

that could hinder the achievement of objectives. Control activities represent the implementation of policies and procedures designed to ensure that activities are carried out in accordance with regulations. Information and communication relate to the availability and delivery of relevant and quality information, while monitoring reflects ongoing efforts to evaluate the effectiveness of the internal control system. The indicators and measurement items for this variable refer to the research by Sulistyani, et al. (2022)

The Leadership Style variable (X2) is measured using five indicators, namely the relationship between leaders and subordinates, task structure, position of power, task delegation, and leader ethics. The indicator of the relationship between leaders and subordinates describes the quality of interaction and communication between leaders and staff. Task structure reflects the clarity of the division of roles and work responsibilities, while position of power indicates the level of authority of leaders in making decisions. Task delegation describes the ability of leaders to distribute authority proportionally, while leader ethics reflects exemplary behavior and integrity in exercising leadership. The measurement of these variables is adapted from an instrument developed by Indrapraja, et al. (2021)

Furthermore, the Anti-Fraud Awareness variable (X3) is operationalized through three main indicators, namely a culture of ethics and honesty, process control and evaluation, and the monitoring process. Ethical culture and honesty reflect the values of integrity instilled in the organization. Process control and evaluation describe awareness of the importance of compliance with work procedures and continuous evaluation, while the monitoring process reflects the active role of supervision in preventing fraud. The development of indicators and question items for this variable refers to Reskia, (2022)

The General Procurement Plan Information System Application (SiRUP) variable (X4) is measured through three indicators, namely transparency, accountability, and cost efficiency. The transparency indicator reflects the openness of procurement information to the public, the accountability indicator describes the ease of tracing and accountability of the procurement process, while the cost efficiency indicator reflects the system's ability to minimize planning errors and budget waste. The formulation of these variable indicators is based on official guidelines and studies related to SiRUP published by the Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency LKPP, (2023)

The Fraud Prevention (Y) variable is operationalized based on four main dimensions, namely opportunity, pressure, capability, and rationalization. These four dimensions are adapted from the concepts of the Fraud Triangle and Fraud Diamond. The opportunity dimension reflects weaknesses in supervision or systems that can be exploited to commit fraud. The pressure dimension describes certain pressures or demands, such as performance targets or financial needs. The capability dimension indicates an individual's capacity to exploit system weaknesses, while the rationalization dimension reflects an individual's justification for committing fraud. The indicators and measurement items for this variable refer to the research by Sakti, et al. (2022)

Drawing Path Diagrams

Figure 2. Drawing Path Diagrams

Based on Figure 2 presents the path diagram of the research model, illustrating the structural and measurement relationships among the latent variables analyzed using a Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach. The model consists of four exogenous variables, Internal Control System (X1), Leadership Style (X2), Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3), and SiRUP Application (X4), and one endogenous variable, namely Fraud Prevention (Y).

Each latent variable is measured by multiple observed indicators. The Internal Control System (X1) is represented by indicators X1.1 to X1.5, reflecting key components such as the control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring. Leadership Style (X2) is measured using indicators X2.1 to X2.9, which capture leadership behaviors related to direction, motivation, communication, and ethical influence. Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3) is operationalized through indicators X3.1 to X3.8, representing employees' understanding, sensitivity, and attitudes toward fraud risks. Meanwhile, the SiRUP Application (X4) is measured by indicators X4.1 to X4.8, reflecting system transparency, accessibility, usefulness, and support for procurement accountability. Fraud Prevention (Y) is measured using indicators Y1 to Y8, which describe preventive mechanisms, detection efforts, and compliance in procurement activities.

Structurally, the diagram shows direct paths from X1, X2, X3, and X4 to Y, indicating that each independent variable is hypothesized to have a direct influence on fraud prevention. These relationships are grounded in Fraud Triangle Theory, Agency Theory, and the Theory of Planned Behavior, which collectively explain how organizational controls, leadership behavior, individual awareness, and technology-based systems contribute to reducing fraud opportunities, rationalization, and agency problems.

Overall, the path diagram in Figure 2 provides a clear representation of both the measurement model and the structural model, demonstrating how observed indicators form latent constructs and how these constructs interact to explain fraud prevention in the procurement of goods and services.

Regarding sample size, although this study used 72 respondents, this number is considered adequate in the PLS-SEM framework. Structurally, the endogenous variable has four predictor paths, so based on the inverse square root rule and gamma-exponential method in PLS-SEM, this sample size has exceeded the minimum requirement for detecting structural effects with a significance level of 5%. Furthermore, statistical power evaluation (post-hoc power analysis) shows that the sample size used has adequate power (>0.80) to detect moderate to strong effects in the structural model. Thus, although not aiming for statistical generalization, the sample size in this study is strong enough to support testing the hypothesized causal relationships in the model.

Overall, Figure 2 presents a comprehensive representation of both the measurement model and the structural model, while also showing that the model design and sample size used have met the methodological requirements of PLS-SEM to explain the factors that influence fraud prevention in the procurement of goods and services.

Distribution of Questionnaires

The following table details the distribution and returns of questionnaires:

Table 1. Questionnaire Distribution and Return Rate

Description	Amount
Questionnaires distributed	72
Questionnaires returned	72
Questionnaires not returned	0
Questionnaire return rate	100%

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that 72 questionnaires were distributed to respondents and all of them were returned in good condition. This shows that the questionnaire return rate reached 100%, so the data obtained can be considered complete and representative for further analysis.

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The descriptive statistics used in this study are minimum value, maximum value, mean, and standard deviation. Accordingly, the category ranges are defined as 1.00–1.80 (very low), 1.81–2.60 (low), 2.61–3.40 (moderate), 3.41–4.20 (high), and 4.21–5.00 (very high). The descriptive statistics of the variables are presented in Table 2.

Based on Table 2, the descriptive statistical results in Table 2, all research variables are classified as being in the high category, based on the mean score criteria of a five-point Likert scale. In this study, mean values ranging from 3.41 to 4.20 are categorized as high, while values above 4.20 are considered very high. This classification follows the common interval approach used in Likert-scale data analysis.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

	N	Min	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
X1	72	1	5	3,597	0,995	-0,318	-0,578
X2	72	1	5	3,861	0,918	-0,598	0,168
X3	72	1	5	3,917	0,982	-1,265	1,714
X4	72	1	5	3,778	0,583	0,078	-0,345
Y	72	1	5	4,111	0,756	-1,177	2,119

The Internal Control System (X1) variable has a mean score of 3.597, placing it in the high category, with negative skewness indicating that respondents tended to provide higher ratings. The Leadership Style (X2) variable records a mean of 3.861, also categorized as high, reflecting positive perceptions of leadership practices within the organization.

The Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3) variable shows the highest mean among the independent variables at 3.917, which falls within the high category, accompanied by strong negative skewness and high kurtosis, suggesting that respondents' responses were concentrated at the upper end of the scale.

The SiRUP Application (X4) variable has a mean value of 3.778, classified as high, with a relatively small standard deviation, indicating consistent perceptions among respondents regarding the implementation of the system.

Meanwhile, the Fraud Prevention (Y) variable records the highest overall mean of 4.111, which lies at the upper bound of the high category and approaches the very high category, combined with a left-skewed distribution and high kurtosis. This finding indicates that fraud prevention practices in regional public hospitals across Lombok Island are perceived by most respondents as being implemented effectively.

Evaluation of Measurement Models (Outer Model)

Convergent Validity

Convergent Validity is a validity test to determine the extent to which a measurement indicator correlates with a construct. The convergent validity value can be seen from the factor loading value, which must be greater than 0.7.

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the results of the factor loading analysis for all indicators for each construct have a value greater than 0.7. This shows that each indicator can measure each variable in the study.

Table 3. Loading Factor Values

Variable	Indicator	Factor Loading
Internal Control System (X1)	X1.1	0,870
	X1.2	0,746
	X1.3	0,891
	X1.4	0,862
	X1.5	0,864
Leadership Style (X2)	X2.1	0,714
	X2.2	0,717
	X2.3	0,771
	X2.4	0,754
	X2.5	0,848
	X2.6	0,787
	X2.7	0,814
	X2.8	0,825
	X2.9	0,852
	X2.10	0,773
Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3)	X3.1	0,903
	X3.2	0,746
	X3.3	0,809
	X3.4	0,905
	X3.5	0,814
	X3.6	0,881
	X3.7	0,894
	X3.8	0,716
	X4.1	0,846
	X4.2	0,893
	X4.3	0,896
SiRUP Application (X4)	X4.4	0,824
	X4.5	0,729
	X4.6	0,864
	X4.7	0,890
	X4.8	0,839
Fraud Prevention (Y)	Y.1	0,821
	Y.2	0,743
	Y.3	0,836
	Y.4	0,728
	Y.5	0,812
	Y.6	0,810
	Y.7	0,856
	Y.8	0,791

Next is to determine convergent validity at the AVE level. This study uses a validation level of 0.50. The AVE value is acceptable and considered valid if it is greater than 0.50. However, if the value is less than 0.50, this indicates that there are still many errors in the indicators of the construct variance.

The outer model evaluation was conducted to assess the quality of the relationship between the indicators and the constructs measured in the study. The outer model assessment was examined through several main criteria, namely the outer loading value, Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and construct reliability as indicated by the composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values. These values are presented in the table below.

Table 4. AVE, Cronbach's Alpha, and Composite Reliability Values

Variable	AVE	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Internal Control System (X1)	0.719	0,901	0,903
Leadership Style (X2)	0.619	0,931	0,936
Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3)	0.699	0,938	0,944
SiRUP Application (X4)	0.853	0,853	0,832
Fraud Prevention (Y)	0.579	0,890	0,909

Based on Table 4, the measurement model demonstrates satisfactory levels of convergent validity and internal consistency reliability. The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values for all constructs exceed the recommended threshold of 0.50, indicating that each latent variable explains more than half of the variance of its indicators. This confirms adequate convergent validity for the Internal Control System (0.719), Leadership Style (0.619), Anti-Fraud Awareness (0.699), SiRUP Application (0.853), and Fraud Prevention (0.579) constructs.

Furthermore, the reliability assessment shows that all constructs achieve Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values above the minimum acceptable level of 0.70. Cronbach's Alpha values range from 0.853 to 0.938, while Composite Reliability values range from 0.832 to 0.944, indicating strong internal consistency among the indicators used to measure each construct. These results suggest that the measurement instruments are reliable and consistently capture the underlying latent variables.

Overall, the findings confirm that the constructs employed in this study meet the required criteria for both validity and reliability, thereby supporting the adequacy of the measurement model for subsequent structural model analysis.

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity assesses the extent to which a construct is empirically distinct from other constructs in the model. In this study, discriminant validity was evaluated using the cross-loading criterion, whereby the loading of each indicator on its associated construct must be higher than its loadings on other constructs.

The results indicate that all indicators load more strongly on their respective latent variables than on any other constructs, demonstrating adequate discriminant validity. This finding confirms that each construct captures a unique conceptual domain and is not excessively correlated with other variables in the model.

Thus, the measurement model satisfies the discriminant validity requirement, ensuring that Internal Control System, Leadership Style, Anti-Fraud Awareness, SiRUP

Application, and Fraud Prevention are empirically distinguishable constructs and suitable for further structural model analysis.

Tabel 5. Cross Loading

	X1	X2	X3	X4	Y
X1.1	0,870	0,411	0,564	-0,161	0,607
X1.2	0,746	0,425	0,576	-0,228	0,603
X1.3	0,891	0,507	0,522	-0,231	0,645
X1.4	0,862	0,484	0,522	-0,108	0,675
X1.5	0,864	0,391	0,530	-0,160	0,589
X2.1	0,486	0,714	0,608	-0,170	0,577
X2.2	0,254	0,773	0,255	-0,109	0,474
X2.3	0,474	0,717	0,533	-0,182	0,497
X2.4	0,500	0,771	0,400	-0,226	0,637
X2.5	0,271	0,754	0,240	-0,147	0,469
X2.6	0,376	0,848	0,353	-0,218	0,500
X2.7	0,560	0,787	0,549	-0,164	0,712
X2.8	0,408	0,814	0,422	-0,143	0,570
X2.9	0,348	0,825	0,420	-0,129	0,643
X2.10	0,359	0,852	0,317	-0,103	0,486
X3.1	0,580	0,370	0,903	-0,110	0,557
X3.2	0,531	0,544	0,746	-0,253	0,705
X3.3	0,486	0,544	0,809	-0,102	0,602
X3.4	0,566	0,405	0,905	-0,129	0,540
X3.5	0,480	0,319	0,814	-0,089	0,511
X3.6	0,555	0,464	0,881	-0,079	0,641
X3.7	0,599	0,423	0,894	-0,080	0,598
X3.8	0,445	0,457	0,716	-0,123	0,426
X4.1	-0,011	-0,114	0,001	0,846	-0,094
X4.2	0,103	-0,087	0,127	0,893	-0,113
X4.3	0,125	0,134	0,031	0,896	0,050
X4.4	-0,184	-0,141	-0,145	0,824	-0,238
X4.5	-0,107	-0,139	-0,117	0,729	-0,186
X4.6	0,235	0,076	0,167	0,864	0,184
X4.7	0,101	0,122	0,096	0,890	-0,009
X4.8	0,087	0,091	0,023	0,839	0,024
Y.1	0,357	0,238	0,222	-0,109	0,821
Y.2	0,464	0,615	0,519	-0,294	0,743
Y.3	0,622	0,562	0,613	-0,366	0,836
Y.4	0,650	0,491	0,425	-0,080	0,728
Y.5	0,628	0,601	0,572	-0,142	0,812
Y.6	0,628	0,592	0,487	-0,218	0,810
Y.7	0,600	0,636	0,734	-0,237	0,856
Y.8	0,508	0,569	0,554	-0,341	0,791

Based on Table 5, the cross-loading test results show that the loading value of each indicator on the construct it measures is higher than the loading of that indicator on other constructs. In addition, discriminant validity was also evaluated using the Heterotrait–Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) criterion.

Tabel 6. Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HMMT)

Variable	HTMT
X1	0.825
X2	0.770
X3	0.738
X4	0.334

Based on Table 6, the HTMT values for all constructs are below the recommended threshold of 0.90, indicating adequate discriminant validity. The highest HTMT value is observed for the Internal Control System (X1) construct at 0.825, followed by Leadership Style (X2) at 0.770, Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3) at 0.738, and the SiRUP Application (X4) at 0.334. These results suggest that each construct is empirically distinct and that there is no excessive conceptual overlap among the latent variables.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the measurement model satisfies the discriminant validity requirement, and all constructs are suitable for further structural model analysis.

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Multicollinearity Assessment

Multicollinearity among the predictor constructs was examined using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to ensure that collinearity does not bias the estimation of the structural model. VIF values were assessed for all exogenous latent variables predicting the endogenous construct, Fraud Prevention. According to established guidelines in PLS-SEM, VIF values below the threshold of 5.0 indicate the absence of critical multicollinearity issues, while more conservative criteria suggest a threshold of 3.3.

Table 7. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

	VIF
X1 → Y	1.862
X2 → Y	1.542
X3 → Y	1.862
X4 → Y	1.059

Based on Table 7, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values for all independent variables (X1, X2, X3, and X4) toward the dependent variable (Y) are below the recommended threshold. The VIF values are 1.862 for X1, 1.542 for X2, 1.862 for X3, and 1.059 for X4.

These results indicate that there is no multicollinearity problem among the predictor variables in the structural model. All VIF values are well below the critical cut-off value of 5.0, and even below the more conservative threshold of 3.3, suggesting that each independent variable contributes distinct and non-redundant information in explaining the dependent variable.

Therefore, the structural model can be considered free from collinearity issues, and the estimated path coefficients can be interpreted reliably.

Path Coefficients

Structural model evaluation (inner model) was conducted to analyze the relationship between latent variables and test research hypotheses. The results are presented in the table below.

Table 8. Path Coefficient Analysis Results

	Original sample	t statistics	P values	Conclusion
X1 → Y	0,352	4,026	0,000	Accepted
X2 → Y	0,379	4,070	0,000	Accepted
X3 → Y	0,254	2,886	0,004	Accepted
X4 → Y	-0,112	1,193	0,233	Rejected

Based on Table 8, the results of the analysis for testing the research hypothesis can be described as follows:

First Hypothesis Testing (H₁)

Based on the test results in Table, the Internal Control System variable (X1) has an original sample value of 0.352, a t-statistic value of 4.026 greater than 1.66, and a p-value of 0.000 less than 0.05, so H₁ is accepted. This result shows that the Internal Control System (X1) has a positive and significant effect on Fraud Prevention (Y). This means that the better the implementation of internal controls, including the control environment, risk assessment, control activities, information and communication, and monitoring, the more effective the organization's efforts in preventing fraud.

Testing the Second Hypothesis (H₂)

Based on the test results in Table, the Leadership Style (X2) variable has an original sample value of 0.379, a t-statistic value of 4.070, which is greater than 1.66, and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Thus, H₂ is accepted. These results indicate that Leadership Style (X2) has a positive and significant effect on Fraud Prevention (Y). This means that the better the leadership style applied, including harmonious relationships with subordinates, clear work instructions, fair distribution of tasks, appropriate use of power, and ethical leadership role modeling, the stronger the effect on fraud prevention efforts in the organization.

Testing the Third Hypothesis (H₃)

Based on the test results in Table, the Anti-Fraud Awareness variable (X₃) has an original sample value of 0.254, a t-statistic value of 2.886 greater than 1.66, and a p-value of 0.004 which is less than 0.05. Thus, H₃ is accepted. These results indicate that Anti-Fraud Awareness (X₃) has a positive and significant effect on Fraud Prevention (Y). This means that the higher the anti-fraud awareness of employees, as reflected in their understanding of ethics, compliance with SOPs, process evaluation, and internal supervision, the more effective the organization's efforts in preventing fraud will be.

Testing the Fourth Hypothesis (H₄)

Based on the test results in Table, the SiRUP Application (X₄) variable obtained an original sample value of -0.112, a t-statistic value of 1.193, which is less than 1.66, and a p-value of 0.233, which is greater than 0.05. Thus, H₄ is rejected. These results indicate that the SiRUP Application (X₄) does not have a significant effect on Fraud Prevention (Y). Although SiRUP facilitates transparency, accountability, and efficiency in the procurement process, empirical data shows that its use has not contributed directly to reducing the potential for fraud.

F-Square

The F-square test is conducted to examine the effect of variables at the structural level. The F-square value is divided into three categories: the first is when the F-square value is 0.02, which means low; the second is when the value is 0.15, which means moderate; and the third is when the value is 0.35, which means high (Hair, et al. 2021). The following table shows the F-square values for each variable.

Table 9. F Square

Variable	<i>F-Square</i>
Internal Control System (X ₁)	0,262
Leadership Style (X ₂)	0,367
Anti-Fraud Awareness (X ₃)	0,137
SiRUP application (X ₄)	0,047

Based on Table 9, the F-square test was conducted to assess the effect size of each independent variable on fraud prevention. Referring to Hair et al. (2021), f-square values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 indicate small, moderate, and large effects, respectively. The results show that the Internal Control System (X₁) has a moderate effect ($f^2 = 0.262$), indicating a substantial contribution to fraud prevention. Leadership Style (X₂) exhibits a large effect ($f^2 = 0.367$), suggesting that it is the most influential factor in preventing fraud. Anti-Fraud Awareness (X₃) demonstrates a small-to-moderate effect ($f^2 = 0.137$), indicating a limited but meaningful influence. In contrast, the SiRUP application (X₄) shows a small effect ($f^2 = 0.047$), implying that its role in fraud prevention is minimal and not dominant.

R-Square

The following is the R-Square table.

Table 10. R Square

Variable	R-Square
Fraud Prevention (Y)	0,746

Based on Table 10, the R-square value for the fraud prevention variable (Y) is 0.746. Referring to Chin (1998) in Ghozali and Latan (2015), R-square values of 0.67, 0.33, and 0.19 indicate good, moderate, and weak explanatory power, respectively. Therefore, an R-square of 0.746 indicates that the research model has strong predictive capability. The exogenous variables—Internal Control System (X1), Leadership Style (X2), Anti-Fraud Awareness (X3), and the SiRUP application (X4)—collectively explain 74.6% of the variance in fraud prevention.

This finding suggests that the proposed model provides a strong explanation of fraud prevention in public hospitals. However, the remaining 25.4% of the variance is influenced by other factors not included in the model, such as organizational culture, external oversight, top management commitment, individual moral values, work pressure, reward and punishment systems, and organizational risk management policies.

Discussion

The Effect of Internal Control Systems on Fraud Prevention

Based on the analysis results, the Internal Control System variable (X1) shows an original sample value of 0.352, a t-statistic value of 4.026, which is greater than the critical value of 1.66, and a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Thus, the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted, meaning that the Internal Control System has a positive and significant effect on Fraud Prevention in Regional General Hospitals on the Island of Lombok.

Based on the respondents' answers, the average value of the Internal Control System variable is in the high category, which illustrates that most respondents consider the internal control of regional public hospitals to be effective, especially in terms of the control environment, control activities, risk assessment, information and communication, and monitoring. This positive perception indicates that the internal control mechanism in regional public hospitals is capable of limiting the opportunity for irregularities in the procurement of goods and services.

This finding is in line with the Fraud Triangle Theory, particularly the element of opportunity, where a strong internal control system can close opportunities for individuals to commit fraud. When an organization has strict procedures, clear division of tasks, and continuous monitoring, the opportunities for perpetrators to abuse their authority become smaller.

Furthermore, in relation to Agency Theory, internal control systems are necessary to monitor the behavior of agents (employees, procurement committees, or management) so that they act in accordance with the interests of the principal (the government and the public). Good control mechanisms will minimize agency conflicts and reduce the potential for fraud due to asymmetric information or moral hazard in the management of goods and services procurement. The results of this study are also consistent with several previous studies. The research by Ramadani, et al. (2023) shows that internal control has a significant effect in reducing the potential for fraud in the public sector.

Thus, the results of this study confirm that the implementation of an effective Internal Control System plays an important role in preventing fraud in the procurement of goods and services at Regional General Hospitals throughout Lombok Island. A strong internal control system not only improves compliance with procedures, but also creates a more transparent, accountable, and fraud-minimized organizational environment.

The Influence of Leadership Style on Fraud Prevention

Based on the analysis results, the Leadership Style variable (X2) shows an original sample value of 0.379, a t-statistic value of 4.070 which is greater than 1.66, and a p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Thus, the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted, which means that Leadership Style has a positive and significant effect on Fraud Prevention in Regional General Hospitals throughout Lombok Island.

Based on the respondents' answers, the Leadership Style variable is in the high category, indicating that the majority of respondents consider that the leadership at regional public hospitals has demonstrated effective leadership characteristics, such as openness to subordinates, clarity of work instructions, fair distribution of tasks, decision-making ability, and exemplary ethics and integrity. This perception shows that the role of leadership is very influential in encouraging the creation of a transparent work environment that is free from fraudulent behavior.

From the perspective of Fraud Triangle Theory, strong and ethical leadership plays a role in suppressing the element of rationalization, where fraudulent acts are often committed by perpetrators because they feel that their actions can be justified. Leaders who consistently demonstrate moral exemplary behavior are able to eliminate this justification, making fraud easier to prevent. Good leadership also influences the pressure element, as supportive leaders can reduce work pressure that has the potential to cause fraud.

Furthermore, in the context of Agency Theory, leaders act as the main controllers who ensure that agents, namely employees and procurement committees, act in accordance with the interests of the principal (government, organization, and society). A firm, ethical, and open leadership style can reduce moral hazard and information asymmetry problems, thereby preventing fraud in the procurement of goods and services.

The findings of this study are in line with the results of previous studies. (Budiantoro, & Lapae, 2022) research shows that leadership style has a significant effect on fraud prevention efforts in the public sector, especially when leaders are able to set an ethical

example. Research by (Reskia, 2022) also found that effective leadership can build an anti-fraud organizational culture through clear communication and visionary leadership.

Thus, this study confirms that leadership style plays an important role in preventing fraud in the procurement of goods and services at Regional General Hospitals throughout Lombok Island. Effective leadership not only builds employee discipline and compliance but also creates a culture of integrity that is sustainable within the organization.

The Effect of Anti-Fraud Awareness on Fraud Prevention

Based on the analysis results, the Anti-Fraud Awareness variable (X3) has an original sample value of 0.254, a t-statistic value of 2.886, which is greater than 1.66, and a p-value of 0.004, which is less than 0.05. Thus, the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted, which means that Anti-Fraud Awareness has a positive and significant effect on Fraud Prevention in Regional General Hospitals on the Island of Lombok.

Based on the respondents' answers, the Anti-Fraud Awareness variable is in the high category, which indicates that RSUD employees have a good level of awareness regarding the importance of fraud prevention. Employees assessed that work ethics, integrity, implementation of SOPs, evaluation of task performance, and periodic supervision have been implemented well. This high level of awareness contributes to the formation of an organizational culture that is sensitive to potential irregularities and encourages every employee to act honestly and professionally in the procurement of goods and services.

From the perspective of Fraud Triangle Theory, anti-fraud awareness plays a role in suppressing the element of rationalization, which is the process by which perpetrators seek justification for their fraudulent actions. When employees have a strong understanding of the risks, impacts, and legal sanctions associated with fraud, there is less room for rationalization. In addition, increased awareness can also reduce the element of opportunity because employees become more aware of system loopholes that can be exploited for fraud and more compliant with SOPs.

Furthermore, in the context of Agency Theory, anti-fraud awareness is an important mechanism for reducing conflicts between principals and agents. When employees (agents) understand the professional responsibilities and ethics that must be adhered to, the potential for moral hazard and abuse of authority will be reduced. This supports the creation of a more accountable working relationship between employees and the organization.

The results of this study are consistent with a number of previous studies. The study by Limbong & Pramukty, (2023) shows that the level of anti-fraud awareness significantly affects an organization's ability to prevent fraud, especially in the public sector. Meanwhile, Reskia, (2022) emphasized that high anti-fraud awareness is directly proportional to increased employee compliance and the effectiveness of control systems within organizations. Thus, this study confirms that Anti-Fraud Awareness is one of the key factors that support efforts to prevent fraud in the procurement of goods and services at Regional General Hospitals throughout Lombok Island. High employee awareness of

the risks and impacts of fraud can strengthen organizational integrity and minimize the chances of irregularities occurring.

The Effect of the SiRUP Application on Fraud Prevention

Based on the analysis results, the SiRUP application (X4) shows an original sample value of -0.112 , a t-statistic of 1.193 (<1.66), and a p-value of 0.233 (>0.05). Therefore, the fourth hypothesis (H4) is rejected, indicating that the SiRUP application does not have a significant effect on fraud prevention in goods and services procurement at Regional General Hospitals across Lombok Island. This finding highlights a gap between the normative objectives of the SiRUP system and its practical implementation.

From a functional perspective, SiRUP primarily operates at the procurement planning and publication stage through the disclosure of the General Procurement Plan (RUP). However, fraudulent practices in procurement more frequently occur during subsequent stages, such as vendor selection, bid evaluation, contract awarding, and contract execution. As these operational stages are not fully governed by SiRUP, transparency at the planning stage alone is insufficient to effectively reduce fraud risk.

According to Fraud Triangle Theory, SiRUP is designed to reduce the opportunity element of fraud by enhancing transparency and public access to procurement information. Nevertheless, transparency without active supervision, enforcement of sanctions, and integration with other internal control mechanisms does not adequately eliminate opportunities for fraud. Discrepancies between system-reported data and actual practices (implementation gaps) may still enable fraudulent behavior.

From the standpoint of Agency Theory, SiRUP functions as an information disclosure mechanism that reduces information asymmetry between principals (government and society) and agents (procurement officials). However, strategic and technical procurement decisions remain largely under the control of agents. As long as agents retain high discretion and internal monitoring mechanisms are weak, increased transparency through SiRUP alone is insufficient to significantly reduce moral hazard.

Furthermore, based on the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), the use of SiRUP has not fully strengthened employees' perceived behavioral control. Although the system is in place, employees may not perceive that their actions are strictly monitored or that non-compliance will result in direct personal consequences. As a result, fraudulent intentions may not be substantially reduced. This condition is exacerbated by limitations in human resource capacity, insufficient technical training, and the perception of SiRUP as a formal administrative requirement rather than a substantive control tool.

In summary, the findings indicate that SiRUP is necessary but not sufficient for effective fraud prevention. While the application plays an important role in promoting transparency in procurement planning, it cannot independently prevent fraud without strong internal controls, ethical leadership, continuous supervision, and an organizational culture that emphasizes anti-fraud values. Consequently, the effectiveness of SiRUP in preventing procurement fraud depends largely on the quality of implementation, system

integration, and organizational commitment rather than on the mere existence of the application.

Conclusion

Based on the results of inner model testing using PLS-SEM, it was found that Internal Control Systems, Leadership Style, and Anti-Fraud Awareness have a positive and significant effect on the Prevention of Fraud in the Procurement of Goods and Services. This means that the better the implementation of internal control, the more effective the leadership style applied, and the higher the level of anti-fraud awareness among employees, the stronger the efforts to prevent fraud in the procurement process at hospitals throughout Lombok Island. These three variables have been proven to make an important contribution to promoting transparent and accountable procurement.

On the other hand, the SiRUP application did not show a significant effect on fraud prevention. This indicates that the existence of the application alone is not sufficient to prevent fraud in procurement. The use of SiRUP may not have been optimal or may have only been used for administrative purposes, so it has not been able to have a real impact on fraud prevention efforts. Overall, the results of this study show that internal organizational factors and the behavior of officials play a more dominant role than technological tools. Therefore, strengthening the monitoring system, improving the quality of leadership, and developing an anti-fraud culture are strategic steps in minimizing the risk of fraud in the procurement of goods and services.

Future Research Directions

Despite its contributions, this study has several limitations that provide opportunities for future research. First, this study employed purposive sampling, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Future studies are encouraged to use probability sampling techniques, such as stratified or cluster sampling, and involve a larger number of hospitals or regions to enhance external validity.

Second, this research focused on internal control systems, leadership style, anti-fraud awareness, and the use of the SiRUP application. Future research may expand the model by incorporating additional variables, such as organizational culture, ethical climate, top management commitment, reward and punishment systems, whistleblowing mechanisms, individual moral reasoning, and work pressure, which may further explain fraud prevention behavior.

Third, this study relied solely on self-reported questionnaire data, which may be subject to response bias and social desirability effects. Future research could adopt a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews, focus group discussions, or document analysis, to obtain deeper insights into the actual implementation of fraud prevention mechanisms.

Fourth, the use of a cross-sectional research design limits the ability to capture changes in behavior over time. Future studies are recommended to apply a longitudinal design to

better observe the dynamic effects of leadership, control systems, and digital applications such as SiRUP on fraud prevention.

Finally, regarding the SiRUP application, future research should examine not only its existence but also the quality of implementation, system integration with other procurement platforms (e.g., e-procurement, SPSE), user competence, and enforcement mechanisms, to better assess its real impact on fraud prevention.

Research Implications

Practical Implications

This study shows that leadership style and internal control systems play a crucial role in preventing procurement fraud in public hospitals. Therefore, hospital management should prioritize ethical leadership development and consistently strengthen internal control mechanisms, particularly in procurement activities. In addition, anti-fraud awareness needs to be continuously enhanced through training and socialization programs to foster a strong integrity culture among employees. The limited impact of the SiRUP application indicates that digital systems alone are insufficient; effective fraud prevention requires active supervision and integration with internal control practices.

Policy Implications

From a policy perspective, the findings suggest the need to strengthen regulations related to ethical leadership, internal control, and procurement governance in public hospitals. Policymakers should ensure that anti-fraud education and competency development are formally integrated into human resource policies. Furthermore, the effectiveness of SiRUP should be improved through better system integration, monitoring mechanisms, and enforcement, so that digital procurement tools can function as effective instruments for fraud prevention rather than merely administrative requirements.

Research Limitations

This study has significant methodological limitations, particularly regarding the sampling strategy used. This study applied purposive sampling with a relatively limited number of respondents, namely 72 respondents, all of whom were from Regional General Hospitals (RSUD) on the island of Lombok. Although this approach was deliberately chosen to ensure that respondents had direct involvement, knowledge, and sufficient experience in the procurement of goods and services, this strategy inherently limits the level of generalization of the research findings.

The use of purposive sampling means that the research results reflect the perceptions and practices of a specific group with specific job characteristics and functions, so they cannot be assumed to represent the entire population of hospital employees, let alone other public sector institutions. Thus, the findings of this study cannot be statistically generalized to hospitals outside Lombok Island or to public organizations with different scales, complexities, and governance systems, such as ministries, state-owned enterprises, or local governments with more advanced levels of procurement digitization.

References

- Abutabenjeh, S., Al-Shboul, M., & Al-Omari, A. (2023). Prevention of fraud in public procurement through electronic procurement systems. *Journal of Contemporary Accounting*, 5(2), 101–115.
- ACFE. (2024). *Report to the Nations: Global study on occupational fraud and abuse*. Austin, TX: ACFE.
- Adenodi, D. W., Okehigbeme, I. S., & Eneh, N. (2025). Effect of procurement fraud detection and prevention on organizational integrity in public sector organizations. *Journal of Finance and Accounting Research*, 7(1), 45–60.
- Ajzen, I., & Fishbein, M. (1980). (1980). *Understanding attitudes and predicting social behavior*. NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Budiantoro, H., Aprillivia, N. D., & Lapae, K. (2022). The effect of GCG implementation, anti-fraud awareness, and employee integrity on fraud prevention. *Journal of Business Orientation and Entrepreneurship*, 3(1), 28–39.
- Chen, H., Yang, D., Zhang, J. H., & Zhou, H. (2020). Internal controls, risk management, and cash holdings. *Journal of Corporate Finance*, 64(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcorpfin.2020.101695>
- Cressey, D. R. (1973). *Other people's money: A study in the social psychology of embezzlement*. Montclair, NJ: Patterson Smith.
- Dewi, R. Y. R., & Ariandi, I. (2017). The effect of internal control and anti-fraud awareness on fraud prevention (a survey on inter-governmental organizations). *Journal of Economics, Business and Accountancy Ventura*, 20(1), 113–124.
- Gani, L., Jermias, J., & Fitriany, F. (2021). Leadership style, organizational culture, and fraud prevention in public organizations. *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 6(2), 123–138.
- Ibrahim, M. (2023). Building anti-fraud awareness to strengthen internal control systems in public institutions. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 36(4), 512–528.
- Indrapraja, M. H. D., Agusti, R., & Mela, N. F. (2021). The influence of leadership style, organizational culture, competence, and religiosity on fraud among civil servants. *CURRENT: Journal of Current Accounting and Business Studies*, 2(2), 166–183.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360.
- Limbong, R., Situmorang, M., & Siregar, S. (2023). Anti-fraud awareness, internal

control, and fraud prevention in public sector organizations. *International Journal of Economics and Business Administration*, 11, 89–102.

- Limbong, T. E., Kuntadi, C., & Pramukty, R. (2023). Factors influencing fraud prevention: Internal audit, anti-fraud awareness, and internal auditor independence. *Jurnal Economina*, 2(6), 1451–1461.
- LKPP. (2023). SIRUP system performance report. *Government Goods/Services Procurement Policy Agency*.
- Ramadani, A., Suci, R. G., & Putra, R. S. (2023). The influence of internal control and organizational commitment on fraud prevention at Madani Regional Hospital, Pekanbaru City. *Bilancia: Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 7(3), 633–639.
- Reskia, R. (2022). The influence of internal audit, anti-fraud awareness, organizational commitment, and organizational culture on fraud prevention: A case study of PT Inti Persada Nusantara. *Jurnal Ekonomi Trisakti*, 2(2), 419–432.
- Sakti, F. R., Rahmawati, R., & Hamid, R. S. (2022). The influence of internal control and leadership style on fraud tendencies. *Owner: Accounting Research and Journal*, 6(3), 2759–2766.
- Setiawan, R., Andreas, A., & Nasrizal, N. (2020). The influence of leadership style, employee quality development, and organizational culture on fraud prevention: Internal control effectiveness as a moderating variable (Study on state-owned banks in Pekanbaru). *Bilancia: Jurnal Ilmiah Akuntansi*, 4(3), 322–329.
- Skousen, C. J., Smith, K. R., & Wright, C. J. (2009). Detecting and predicting financial statement fraud: The effectiveness of the fraud triangle. *Journal of Corporate Governance and Firm Performance*, 13, 53–81.
- Sulistiyani and UmmahTama, I. F., Wijaya, A. L., & Nurhayati, P. (2022). The influence of whistleblowing systems, internal control roles, and organizational culture on fraud prevention in hospitals referring Covid-19 patients in Madiun City. *Seminar on Management, Business, and Accounting Innovation (SIMBA)*, 4(1).
- Wardhani, R., Rossieta, H., & Martani, D. (2021). Internal control systems and fraud prevention in public sector organizations. *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, 33(4), 567–589.

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